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Short description

Experimental realization of a detector for a single quantum of radiation by calorimetric means has become popular over the past years. In this context the fluctuations of the electron-phonon heat current are important since they determine the fundamental bound of detectable energy of the radiation quantum. Since the fluctuation-dissipation theorem holds our practical task is to optimize the thermal conductance considering various electronic systems including superconducting proximity structures. Motivated by the experiments that have been performed in the PICO group of Prof. Jukka Pekola from ALLTO University we were supposed to provide an appropriate theoretical description of such an effect.

Theoretical fundamentals

Our theoretical work has been done in the framework of the quasiclassical Keldysh-Green's formalism and the linear response theory. If the electron-electron and phonon-phonon relaxation is sufficiently fast we can assume the thermal equilibrium but the different temperatures of the electrons, T_e , and phonons, T_{ph} . By employing the Kubo formula where the electron-phonon interacting Hamiltonian is treated as a perturbation we end up with the following formula for the electron-phonon heat current:

$$Q_{ph}(T_{ph}, T_e) = \frac{N_0 \tau}{8\pi \rho_0} \left(\frac{p_F^2}{m} \right)^2 \int d\mathbf{R} \int_0^\infty \frac{d\omega}{2\pi} \sum_\lambda \frac{\omega^4}{c_\lambda^5} Q_\lambda \left(\frac{\omega \ell}{c_\lambda} \right) \left(\coth \frac{\omega}{2T_{ph}} - \coth \frac{\omega}{2T_e} \right) I(\mathbf{R}, \omega), \quad (1)$$

where N_0 is the normal density of states at the Fermi level, τ is the electron-impurity scattering time, ρ_0 is the mass density of the material, p_F is the magnitude of the Fermi momentum, c_λ ($\lambda = l, t1, t2$) is speed of sound of the material (one longitudinal and two equal transverse modes), and Q_λ is a function related to the phonon-impurity scattering, and ℓ is the electronic mean free path. The whole information about the electronic properties of the system is contained in the $I(\mathbf{R}, \omega)$ function that is given by

$$I(\mathbf{R}, \omega) = 2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\epsilon \text{Tr} \{ [\hat{g}_0^R(\mathbf{R}; \epsilon_+) - \hat{g}_0^A(\mathbf{R}; \epsilon_+)] [\hat{g}_0^R(\mathbf{R}; \epsilon_-) - \hat{g}_0^A(\mathbf{R}; \epsilon_-)] [n_F(\epsilon_+) - n_F(\epsilon_-)] \},$$

where $\hat{g}_0^{R/A}(\mathbf{R}; \epsilon_\pm)$ is the retarded/advanced component of the quasiclassical Keldysh-Green's matrix, $n_F(\epsilon) = [\exp(\epsilon/T_e) + 1]^{-1}$ is the Fermi distribution, and the frequency dependence is contained in $\epsilon_\pm = \epsilon \pm \omega/2$. If we assume that the temperature difference between electrons and phonons is small, $T_e = T_{ph} = T$, we can define the thermal conductance as a derivative with respect to temperature and whose expression has a similar form as Eq. (1), but with a replacement

$$\left(\coth \frac{\omega}{2T_{ph}} - \coth \frac{\omega}{2T_e} \right) \rightarrow - \frac{\omega}{2T^2 \sinh[\omega/(2T)]}$$

These formulas are extremely general and do not depend on the nature of an electronic system in consideration (it can be normal metal, BCS state, proximity structures etc.).

Applications to superconducting proximity systems

Due to experimental reasons, we are mainly interested in a description of the effect in superconducting proximity systems in the dirty limit, so that $\ell \ll \xi \sim \sqrt{D/2\Delta_0}$, where the quasiclassical Keldysh-Green's function is governed by the Usadel equation. For illustration we present the results for two geometries of the SN proximity systems: SIN contact where a thin normal metal, represented by a single node in Fig. 1(a), is coupled to a homogeneous superconductor via tunnel contact and a thin SN bilayer (see Fig. 1(b)).

Fig. 1. Schematic view of the systems under study: (a) SIN contact where a thin normal metal N is coupled to a superconducting lead S via good tunnel contact of a conductance G_T , (b) SN contact where a thin normal metal of a thickness d_N is coupled to a thin superconductor of a thickness d_S . The interface is characterized by the conductance per unit area $g = G_T/\mathcal{A}$, and $\sigma_{N/S}$ denotes the normal state conductivity of the N/S layer.

To illustrate that the difference between these two systems is significant, we present the local density of states of the N region as a function of energy for various parameters in Fig. 2. Since in the first case we deal with a tunnel junction the inverse proximity effect is suppressed and the spectrum of the normal metal is discrete (see Fig. 2(a)). On the other hand, in the case of a thin SN bilayer the inverse proximity effect takes place and the spectrum is smeared. The main feature in both cases is the presence of a minigap. This leads to significantly suppressed thermal conductance at low temperatures (see Fig. 3). We observe that all the curves lie between the normal (dashed violet line) and the BCS case (dashed gray line) and the rate of suppression at low temperatures strongly depends on the width of the minigap. We conclude that the heat current fluctuations are reduced in the systems whose spectrum has a gap.

In this report we have provided a short overview of our work on a theoretical description of a quantum heat detector that is pursued in a close collaboration with ESR 4 Bayan Karimi and Prof. Jukka Pekola from ALLTO University. The theory is done under the supervision of Prof. Wolfgang Belzig (UKON) and in collaboration with Dr. Denis Basko (CNRS). Writing of a theoretical paper on the topic is in progress.

Fig. 2. Panel (a): The local DOS as a function of energy in the N side of a SIN proximity contact shown in Fig. 1(a) for various values of the Thouless energy that is proportional to the G_T/G_Q , the broadening parameter $\eta/\Delta_0 = 10^{-3}$, and the temperature $T/T_c = 0.01$. Panel (b): The local DOS as a function of energy in the N side of a thin SN proximity system shown in Fig. 1(b) for various thicknesses of the normal layer, the broadening parameter $\eta/\Delta_0 = 10^{-5}$, the thickness of the superconductor $d_S/\xi = 0.5$, the equal conductivities $\sigma_N/g\xi = \sigma_S/g\xi = 1.0$, and the temperature $T/T_c = 0.01$. The dotted lines show to the corresponding local DOS in the S layer.

Fig.3. Panel (a): The thermal conductance as a function of temperature in the N side of a SIN proximity contact shown in Fig. 1(a) for various values of the Thouless energy, $\alpha = c_\ell/\ell\Delta_0 = 1.0$, where ℓ is the electronic mean free path, $\gamma = c/c_\ell = 1.0$, and the broadening parameter $\eta/\Delta_0 = 10^{-5}$. Panel (b): The thermal conductance as a function of temperature in the N side of a thin SN proximity contact shown in Fig. 1(b) for various thicknesses of the N layer, the broadening parameter $\eta/\Delta_0 = 10^{-5}$, $\gamma = c/c_\ell = 1.0$, $\alpha = c/\ell\Delta_0 = 1.0$, the thickness of the S layer $d_S/\xi = 0.5$, and the equal conductivities $\sigma_N/g\xi = \sigma_S/g\xi = 1.0$. The dashed violet and gray lines correspond, respectively, to a bulk normal and BCS state.